

A Novel and Convenient Synthesis of N-Phenylbenzohydroxamic Acid (PBHA)

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A one step process for the preparation of N-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid has been developed. The method yields PBHA of moderately high purity in short reaction time.

N-Phenylbenzohydroxamic acid, abbreviated as PBHA, is prepared in one step by reduction of nitrobenzene with zinc and acetic acid and simultaneously reacting N-phenylhydroxylamine thus formed with benzoyl chloride in diethyl ether, at low temperature. PBHA obtained has been characterized by melting point, ultra violet absorption spectra, and molar absorptivity with vanadium(V). The method proposed here is fast, cheap and gives satisfactory yield as compared to other reported methods. All previously reported synthesis of PBHA required freshly prepared and crystallized phenylhydroxylamine, which was dissolved in hot water or diethyl ether and then reacted with benzoyl chloride at different temperatures in different alkaline mediums¹⁻⁹. All methods described are essentially two step preparation involving a lot of solvent, and long reaction time (about 5 hours) and conversion to PBHA in terms of nitrobenzene is also low. By the method described here the time is reduced to less than one hour and yield of PBHA is also improved (about 60%) with respect to nitrobenzene.

Experimental

12.3 g. (0.1 mole) of nitrobenzene, 15 ml. (approx. 0.2 mole) of glacial acetic acid and 15 ml. ice cold water are taken in a 250 ml. three necked flask, fitted with a mechanical stirrer and separatory funnel. The flask is kept in a freezing mixture. 7 g. (approx. 0.1 mole) of zinc dust are taken. Assuming 60% conversion of nitrobenzene into phenylhydroxylamine, 8.4 g. (0.06 mole) of benzoyl chloride dissolved in 25 ml. diethyl ether is transferred into the separatory funnel. Zinc dust and benzoyl chloride are added to the contents of the three necked flask, slowly with vigorous stirring in the course of about 20 minutes. Temperature is maintained below 2°. As the nitrobenzene gets reduced to phenylhydroxylamine by zinc and acetic acid, it reacts with benzoyl chloride to produce

N-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid, which gets precipitated in the course of reaction. After the reaction, this is filtered along with the unreacted zinc dust. From the filtrate ethereal layer, if present, is separated and ether distilled off. The yellowish white solid obtained from the ethereal layer is combined with the rest of residue and treated with 20-25 ml. concentrated hydrochloric acid to dissolve out the unreacted zinc dust. The solution is cooled and treated with 50ml. of cold water. The PBHA is filtered, and crystallized from benzene petroleum ether. Two to three recrystallizations give pure product, m.p. 121° (Reported value 121°)⁹. Yield 70 to 80%. Molar absorptivity of its vanadium(V) complex in chloroform at 530 nm is 4650 ± 50 liter/mole cm. (Reported 4650 ± 50)¹⁰. Ultraviolet spectra are taken in 95% spectroscopic ethanol in UV VIS Specord, $\lambda_{\max} = 268$ nm, $\epsilon = 8900 \pm 50$ l. mole⁻¹cm⁻¹ (Reported $\lambda_{\max} = 268$ nm, $\epsilon = 8900 \pm 50$ l. mole⁻¹cm⁻¹)⁹.

Note: 1. Higher temperature (even room temperature) and longer addition time of benzoyl chloride yields other products (benzanilide m.p. 163°) from which PBHA is separated with difficulty.

2. Excess of benzoyl chloride and zinc dust give low yield.

3. Presence of excess phenylhydroxylamine is tested with Tollen's reagent after the reaction. If it is still present, then excess benzoyl chloride is added as described in above procedure.

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